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Non-conventional endpoints show higher sulfoxaflor toxicity to *Chironomus riparius* than conventional endpoints in a multistress environment --Manuscript Draft--

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Abstract:	<p>Evidence grows that standard toxicity testing might underestimate the environmental risk of neurotoxic insecticides. Behavioural endpoints such as locomotion and mobility have been suggested as sensitive and ecologically relevant additions to the standard tested endpoints. Possible interactive effects of chemicals and additional stressors are typically overlooked in standardised testing. Therefore, we aimed to investigate how concurrent exposure to environmental stressors (increased temperature and predation cues) and a nicotinic acetylcholine receptor (nAChR)-modulating insecticide ('sulfoxaflor') impact <i>Chironomus riparius</i> across a range of conventional and non-conventional endpoints. We used a multifactorial experimental design encompassing three stressors, sulfoxaflor (2.0-110 µg/L), predation risk (presence/absence of predatory cues), and elevated temperature (20 °C and 23 °C), yielding a total of 24 distinct treatment conditions. To assess potential additive effects, we applied an Independent Action (IA) model to predict the impact on eight endpoints, including conventional endpoints (growth, survival, total emergence, and emergence time) and less conventional endpoints (the size of the adults, swimming abilities and exploration behaviour). For the conventional endpoints, observed effects were either lower than expected or well-predicted by the IA model. In contrast, we found greater than predicted effects of predation cues and temperature in combination with sulfoxaflor on adult size, larval exploration, and swimming behaviour. However, in contrast to the non-conventional endpoints, no conventional endpoints detected interactive effects of the neurotoxic insecticide and the environmental stressors. Acknowledging these interactions, increasing ecological context of ecotoxicological test systems may, therefore, advance environmental risk analysis and interpretation as the safe environmental concentrations of neurotoxic insecticides depend on the context of both the test organism and its environment.</p>
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Dear Editor-in-Chief,

We hereby submit our manuscript entitled "*Non-conventional endpoints show higher sulfoxaflor toxicity to Chironomus riparius than conventional endpoints in a multistress environment*".

Highlights of the paper are:

- Emergence and swimming of *C. riparius* is altered when exposed to sulfoxaflor
- Additional stressors did not change the sensitivity of *C. riparius* to sulfoxaflor
- Conventional endpoints predict no to positive effects of multiple stressors
- Behavioural endpoints showed greater effects than predicted by IA modelling
- Environmental stressors were more influential at higher sulfoxaflor concentrations

As such, we are convinced that this work fits the scope of Aquatic Toxicology. This paper has never been published (not in whole nor substantial part). All persons entitled to authorship have been included.

Furthermore, we have not submitted the manuscript to a preprint server before submitting it to Aquatic Toxicology.

We thank you for considering this manuscript for publication and look forward to discussing any queries.

Yours faithfully,

On behalf of all authors,

Sofie B. Rasmussen, Thijs Bosker, S. Henrik Barmentlo, Olof Berglund, and Martina G. Vijver

Non-conventional endpoints show higher sulfoxaflor toxicity to *Chironomus riparius* than conventional endpoints in a multistress environment

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19

20

21

22 **Abstract**

23 Evidence grows that standard toxicity testing might underestimate the environmental risk of neurotoxic
24 insecticides. Behavioural endpoints such as locomotion and mobility have been suggested as sensitive and
25 ecologically relevant additions to the standard tested endpoints. Possible interactive effects of chemicals
26 and additional stressors are typically overlooked in standardised testing. Therefore, we aimed to
27 investigate how concurrent exposure to environmental stressors (increased temperature and predation
28 cues) and a nicotinic acetylcholine receptor (nAChR)-modulating insecticide ('sulfoxaflor') impact
29 *Chironomus riparius* across a range of conventional and non-conventional endpoints. We used a
30 multifactorial experimental design encompassing three stressors, sulfoxaflor (2.0-110 µg/L), predation
31 risk (presence/absence of predatory cues), and elevated temperature (20 °C and 23 °C), yielding a total of
32 24 distinct treatment conditions. To assess potential additive effects, we applied an Independent Action
33 (IA) model to predict the impact on eight endpoints, including conventional endpoints (growth, survival,
34 total emergence, and emergence time) and less conventional endpoints (the size of the adults, swimming
35 abilities and exploration behaviour). For the conventional endpoints, observed effects were either lower
36 than expected or well-predicted by the IA model. In contrast, we found greater than predicted effects of
37 predation cues and temperature in combination with sulfoxaflor on adult size, larval exploration, and
38 swimming behaviour. However, in contrast to the non-conventional endpoints, no conventional endpoints
39 detected interactive effects of the neurotoxic insecticide and the environmental stressors. Acknowledging
40 these interactions, increasing ecological context of ecotoxicological test systems may, therefore, advance
41 environmental risk analysis and interpretation as the safe environmental concentrations of neurotoxic
42 insecticides depend on the context of both the test organism and its environment.

43

44 **Keywords:**

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46 1 Introduction:

47 Neurotoxic insecticides are ubiquitous in agricultural practices (Costa et al., 2008; Berens et al., 2021;
48 Casillas et al., 2022), and as a result, their residues are commonly detected in surface waters globally
49 (Borsuah et al., 2020; Thompson et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2023). This contamination has raised concerns
50 for aquatic ecosystems, particularly for the health of aquatic organisms (Casillas et al., 2022). Sulfoxaflor
51 is a recently introduced insecticide in the sulfoximine class, whose primary site of action is nerve action
52 (Gauthier & Mabury, 2021). Although classified as a unique class (Sparks et al., 2013), it shares many
53 characteristics with the extensively used neonicotinoids (Cutler et al., 2012). These characteristics have
54 previously been observed to cause effects on aquatic communities, including declines in macro-
55 invertebrate (Van Dijk et al., 2013; Sánchez-Bayo et al., 2016) and insect abundance (Goulson, 2014;
56 Barmantlo et al., 2021).

57 Regulations on pesticides rely on a tiered approach of risk assessments, starting with short-term tests
58 involving single species under standardised conditions (EFSA, 2013; Diepens et al., 2016; Schuijt et al.,
59 2021). However, these conventional toxicity metrics may underestimate the ecological impact of
60 neurotoxic agents in aquatic environments (Vijver et al., 2017; Legradi et al., 2018; de Campos et al.,
61 2022). Sensitivities to neonicotinoid and lufenuron at LOEC levels up to 2500 times lower have been
62 found for multiple organisms, including *Daphnia magna*, *Chironomus riparius* and *Hyalella Azteca* when
63 exposed *in situ* compared to the standard laboratory OECD test (Barmantlo et al., 2018; Brock et al.,
64 2016)

65 Traditional ecotoxicity assessments tend to focus on endpoints such as mortality and reproduction, often
66 not reflecting the species responses that occur before these life-history endpoints (Sarma & Nandini, 2006;
67 Forbes et al., 2017; Legradi et al., 2018). Given the primary mode of action is nerve action for neurotoxic
68 insecticides, behavioural endpoints (e.g., locomotion and mobility) are expected to show higher sensitivity
69 compared to conventional endpoints (Augusiak & Van den Brink, 2016; Weichert et al., 2017). To
70 illustrate, Raby et al. (2018) report a difference in sensitivity of up to three orders of magnitude between a

71 standard endpoint (mortality) and less conventional endpoints (limited swimming behaviour or muscle
72 spasms) of *C. dipterum* larvae when exposed to acute doses of neonicotinoids. Impaired ability to burrow
73 in *C. riparius* larvae has been linked to them being significantly more prone to predation by zebrafish
74 (*Danio rerio*), highlighting the relevance of mobility for survival and, hence, suggesting potential impacts
75 on population dynamics (Langer-Jaesrich et al., 2010). Incorporating behavioural endpoints into
76 ecological risk assessments of neurotoxins holds promise due to their sensitivity and ecological relevance
77 (Ågerstrand et al., 2020; Bownik & Wlodkowic, 2021).

78 There is a low level of environmental realism in lower-tier risk screening, as species are exposed under
79 optimal conditions and often to a single stressor (Holmstrup et al., 2010; Schuijt et al., 2021). Adding
80 stressors in the experimental design, such as elevated surface water temperatures, can alter the sensitivity
81 of aquatic species to chemical exposure (Scherer et al., 2013; Macaulay et al., 2020). This finding pleads
82 for enhancing environmental relevance within the test settings (Holmstrup et al., 2010; Jackson et al.,
83 2016), allowing for a broader impact assessment. Abiotic conditions fluctuate naturally and are in the
84 future likely more subject to change given climate change; lake surface temperatures have increased
85 worldwide by 0.34 °C per decade (Woolway et al., 2020) and are further expected to increase by 2.7 to 7
86 °C in summer periods (Hardenbicker et al., 2017; Rajesh & Rehana, 2022). Higher water and air
87 temperatures can influence vital responses related to organisms' fitness, such as increased metabolism
88 (Shah et al., 2020) and emergence of aquatic insect species (Heye et al., 2019; Dellar et al., 2022).
89 Furthermore, behavioural changes as a result of increased water temperature have been shown for
90 *Diamesa zernyi* (Chironomidae) larvae. However, in contrast to exposure to neurotoxic insecticides,
91 distance and speed were increased compared to controls after just 24 hours of exposure (Lencioni et al.,
92 2021).

93 Moreover, one of the most important biotic forms of stress is predation. Predatory cues can significantly
94 influence the behaviour of prey organisms, which can directly influence exposure as well as response
95 parameters to the toxicant (Langer-Jaesrich et al., 2010). Indirectly, the predatory cues potentially

96 exacerbate the effects of chemical presence (Pestana et al., 2010; van Dievel et al., 2019; Bundschuh et al.,
97 2020). For example, the presence of kairomones from predators in combination with exposure to
98 chlorpromazine hydrochloride can act jointly in decreasing oxygen consumption rates and swimming
99 speed of *D. magna* (de Alkimin et al., 2020). Similarly, chlorpyrifos exposure and predation cues caused
100 additive effects on both growth and cellular energy allocation of damselfly larvae *Ischnura elegans* (van
101 Dievel et al., 2019). It is possible that these additive effects are a response to enhanced effects on
102 locomotion, as both exposures to predation cues and neurotoxic insecticides have been shown to affect
103 similar endpoints, such as decreased movements in aquatic organisms. To date, limited research has been
104 conducted to investigate how a combination of environmental factors affecting similar endpoints, such as
105 elevated temperature and predation stress, jointly impact neurotoxic-induced effects on ecologically
106 relevant sub-lethal biomechanical endpoints.

107 Here, we aim to test to what extent concurrent exposure of benthic *C. riparius* larvae to environmental
108 stressors and a nicotinic acetylcholine receptor (nAChR)-modulating insecticide, sulfoxaflor. We
109 investigate the impact on both lethal and sublethal endpoints and compare the sensitivity of conventional
110 endpoints to behavioural responses. To this end, we used a multifactorial environmental stressor approach
111 and hypothesised that the sensitivity of the organisms increased under stress-on-stress conditions. *C.*
112 *riparius* has been identified as sensitive to neurotoxins under standard conditions (Brock et al., 2016;
113 Casillas et al., 2022), and other studies show that the effects of chemicals on conventional endpoints, as
114 emergence and mortality, are potentiated when combined with one additional form of stress (Pestana et
115 al., 2009; Van Praet et al., 2014; Heye et al., 2019), making *C. riparius* ideal for a combined study of
116 interactions between several stressors. Furthermore, as effects of sulfoxaflor on *C. riparius* have
117 previously been shown to be more pronounced when assessed with non-conventional endpoints
118 (Rasmussen et al., 2024), these endpoints are interesting to assess in a more ecologically relevant setup.

119

120 2 Methods:

121 2.1 Test species

122 For this study, eggs of *C. riparius* were generously provided from a well-established culture maintained
123 by the University of Amsterdam (Amsterdam, the Netherlands). *C. riparius* were acclimated for one
124 generation under standardised laboratory conditions, which included a temperature of 20 °C and a 16-hour
125 light/8-hour dark photoperiod cycle. During the acclimation period, the culture was kept in ISO standard
126 freshwater (NaHCO₃: 67.75 mg/L; CaCl₂: 294 mg/L; MgSO₄: 123.25 mg/L; KCl: 5.75 mg/L) and received
127 bi-weekly feedings of shredded TetraMin corresponding to a rate of 0.5 mg per larvae per day.

128 Additionally, ten crucian carp (*Carassius carassius*, length ~ 10 cm) were supplied by Lund University
129 (Lund, Sweden) and were maintained under identical light conditions at a constant temperature of 20 °C in
130 a 25 L tank filled with the same medium. Adequate aeration was provided, and the carp were continuously
131 fed a diet consisting of commercially available chironomids. These wild-caught fish were part of another
132 study at the Lund University and cared for by professional handlers.

133

134 2.2 Test compound

135 Sulfoxaflor (97.8 % purity; CAS No. 946578-00-3) was purchased from AccuStandard (New Haven, CT,
136 USA). Five different concentrations of sulfoxaflor and a control were used. Dilutions were made from a
137 stock solution kept at 5 C° to limit degradation. The nominal concentrations were: 0, 6.25, 12.5, 30, 80,
138 and 160 µg sulfoxaflor/L. After the initial tests (at 20 °C and 23 °C with no predation cues), the nominal
139 concentrations were altered in subsequent tests to; 0, 30, 62.5, 95, 127.5 and 160 µg/L to improve dose-
140 response curve fit. The latter were tested at 20 °C and 23 °C with predation cues and a repetition of 23 °C
141 with no predation cues. All dilutions were prepared in test medium. Since sulfoxaflor has an aquatic
142 aerobic half-life of 37-88 days (US EPA, 2013), we expected sulfoxaflor to be present throughout the
143 exposure period. Samples of 15 mL were taken on days 0, 1, 8, 9, and 23 to observe the sulfoxaflor

144 concentrations throughout the full duration of the experiment. Samples taken on day 0 were directly taken
145 from the dilutions before adding to the test vessels. On day 8, a total of 50 mL medium per beaker was
146 replaced with fresh dilutions, samples for chemical analysis were taken before locomotive measurements
147 on day 8 and on day 9 to represent concentrations at new equilibrium after exchange of the medium (see
148 *Section 2.3* and *Section 2.4*). Samples were directly stored in the freezer (-20 °C) until chemical analysis
149 could take place.

150
151 Chemical analyses of sulfoxaflor samples were conducted at Leiden University using an LC-MS system
152 (Waters Aquity I-class FTN) coupled to a Mass spec system (SciEX Qtrao 6500) equipped with a
153 corresponding column (Waters ACQUITY UPLC BEH C18; 2.1 mm×50 mm, 1.7 µm). The samples were
154 separated using two eluents: Eluant A (95 % H₂O, 5 % ACN, 0,1 % Formic acid) and Eluant B (95 %
155 ACN, 5 % H₂O, 0,1 % Formic acid) in a gradient for a total of 6 minutes (flow: 0.60 mL min⁻¹; see
156 *supplementary information, A*). The output was scanned using Multi-reaction monitoring in positive ion
157 mode (MRM). The sulfoxaflor stock solution from the exposure scenario was used as the standard, from
158 which a calibration with a range of 0 – 200 µg/L sulfoxaflor was made. An internal standard of
159 Sulfoxaflor-d₃ (Toronto Research Chemicals Inc) was added to all sample vials in a concentration of 10
160 µg/L. Lastly, measurements of all samples were repeated three times to reduce chances of false positives
161 (further details can be found in *supplementary information, A*).

162
163 *2.3 Experimental setup*
164 In this study, a multifactorial experimental design encompassing three stressors—sulfoxaflor (at six
165 different concentrations), predation risk (presence/absence of predatory cues), and temperature (20 °C and
166 23 °C)—was employed, yielding a total of 24 distinct treatment conditions (see *Figure 1*). All treatments
167 followed a similar exposure setup and duration (see *Figure 2*). Dose-response curves for the effects of
168 sulfoxaflor on *C. riparius* were fitted, with each curve corresponding to a specific combination of

169 increased temperature and the presence or absence of predation stress (see *Section 2.5*). In scenarios
 170 involving elevated temperatures, all experimental containers were immersed in a water bath maintained at
 171 a constant temperature of 23 °C throughout the experiment.

Exposure conditions

172
 173 *Figure 1, exposure conditions in the multifactorial setup per scenario. Concentrations are expressed as*
 174 *nominal concentrations of sulfoxaflor in water phase. Note that in the picture, two *C. riparius* are given*
 175 *per jar, representing five individuals as used in our test set-up. N=5 for all treatments.*

176
 177 To prepare the predatory risk treatment, elucient from *C. carassius* and alarm cues from *C. riparius* larvae
 178 were combined. First, the crucian carp were subjected to a three-day fasting period in a housing aquarium
 179 to reduce faecal production (Pestana et al., 2009). Subsequently, ten carp were transferred to a clean
 180 freshwater medium and kept in a well-aerated 25 L aquarium for 24 hours, after which they were returned
 181 to their housing aquarium and fed. The water containing carp exudates was then filtered and frozen at -20
 182 °C until required. Before initialisation of the experiment, the fish stock solution was diluted as necessary.
 183 To induce predation stress, an experimental concentration of 0.1 fish/L was determined as sufficient,
 184 based on prior research (Pestana et al., 2009). For the production of alarm cue stock solution, 50 fourth-
 185 instar *C. riparius* larvae were macerated and dissolved in 50 mL of freshwater medium. The resultant

186 solution was filtered and similarly frozen at -20°C, following the methodology outlined by Pestana et al.
187 (2009). A final concentration of 2 larvae/L was used in combination with predation cues for the predatory
188 risk treatments.

189 Four days before commencing the experiment (see *Figure 2* for the experimental timeline), newly laid egg
190 ropes (<1 day old) were collected from the culture and allowed to hatch under controlled conditions.

191 Larvae were randomly selected for the various treatments. To acclimate the larvae to elevated temperature
192 conditions (23 °C), the temperature was incrementally increased over a 48-hour period, with increments of
193 0.2-0.3 °C every few hours. In each test vessel, 41 g of inorganic sand (grain size ranging from 0.01 to 0.5
194 mm, Plantorama, DK) was added, resulting in a sand depth of approximately 1.5 cm. Prior to use, the sand
195 was autoclaved and rinsed with deionised ('DI') water.

196 On day 0 of the experiment, five first-instar larvae were introduced into each test vessel, with five
197 replicate test vessels per treatment. Continuous aeration starting on day 1 was provided to each test vessel
198 using an aquarium pump. Dissolved oxygen was measured using a portable oxygen meter (WTW Multi
199 3510IDS). Additionally, pH and salinity were determined at the start and end of all test periods. Water
200 evaporation was monitored daily, and DI water was added as necessary to maintain water volumes. Food
201 (TetraMin) was administered every three days at a rate of 0.5 mg per larva per day.

202 To ensure stable chemical exposure throughout the larval phase and to mitigate unwanted algae growth,
203 the total amount of medium in each container was exchanged once on day 8. Monitoring of the
204 experimental setups was continued until day 23, as control larvae were expected to emerge within this
205 timeframe (following OECD guideline 219; OECD, 2004). After emergence, adults were collected,
206 analysed (see *Section 2.4*) and stored in a freezer at -20 °C.

207
 208 *Figure 2, Experimental timeline of the exposure of C. riparius to sulfoxaflor and two different*
 209 *environmental stressors. Note two larvae are for illustration, amounts in the test set up were five larvae*
 210 *per jar.*

211

212 2.4 Endpoints

213 For survival, length, and locomotion measurements all larvae were carefully removed from the beakers on
 214 day 8 and added to two 6-well plates containing medium. Survival was counted as the number of retrieved
 215 larvae per beaker, larvae were considered alive by response to physical stimuli and no visible degradation.
 216 Images were taken from above with an iPhone 14Pro for length measurements of alive individuals.
 217 Analysis of images was performed using ImageJ 1.53e (Wayne Rasband, Maryland, USA; Abramoff et
 218 al., 2004).

219 For locomotion assessment, two 6-well plates (one individual per well) were placed underneath a video
 220 camera (Sony HDR CX405). The approximate distance between camera and subject was 30 cm, and all
 221 individuals were recorded for 10 minutes, directly following a 10 minutes acclimation period. Tracking of
 222 individuals was done using automatic tracking in AnimalTA (Chiara & Kim, 2023). Positions of each
 223 larva in all frames were found by comparing each frame to an automated background and determining the
 224 centre of mass of each larva based on colour. Movement over time was determined by the difference in
 225 positions between each frame; a max of 2 cm distance per frame between positions was added to aid the
 226 software and to lower false positives. After automated tracking, each video was manually evaluated, and

227 the identified positions of larvae were adjusted where needed. Smoothing over 35 frames was done to
228 lower inconsistencies in the precise position due to larvae sizes. Analysed endpoints included swimming
229 ratio (%), average swimming speed (cm/s), and exploration of the arena (cm²). For the swimming ratio, a
230 threshold of 0.5 cm/s was chosen to be sufficient to successfully locate swimming phases and to avoid
231 including non-moving periods. After localising all swimming events, the swimming ratio was calculated
232 as time spent swimming ($v < 0.5$ cm/s) over total recording time. Average velocities were taken per larvae,
233 only including frames that were moving at 0.5 cm/s. Lastly, for continuity, an area of 0.21 cm² per larvae
234 independent of larva size was used for explorations.

235 Living larvae (visually checked on health) were returned to corresponding treatment beaker for
236 measurements of emergence. Emergence was quantified by counting the number of adults in each
237 replicate daily, after the first emerging adult until day 23 (*Figure 2*). Adults were trapped in their
238 respective beakers using parafilm. After removal with a tweezer, all adults were sexed to account for
239 sexual dimorphisms in size, and images were taken for length measurement. The length of the adults was
240 determined using ImageJ, from the tip of the head until the tip of the tail. All data for total emergence,
241 time of emergence, and adult size were pooled for both sexes to optimise replicate numbers, as no
242 significant impact of gender was found.

243

244 2.5 Statistical analyses

245 Potential differences between controls (20°C, no predation cue), further referred to as culture controls of
246 the different exposure scenarios, were tested using a one-way ANOVA, followed by a Tukey's posthoc
247 test. Normality of error distribution was tested with a Shapiro-Wilk test and Levene's test to ensure
248 homogeneity of variances. Furthermore, dose-response curves for the effects of sulfoxaflor on *C. riparius*
249 for each of the four scenarios: predation (presence /absence), and temperature (20 and 23 °C) were
250 performed in R, using the drc package and a 3 par log-logistic function, the corresponding 95 %

251 confidence intervals were calculated by non-linear regression. All dose-response curves were based on
252 data normalised to the treatment with no added sulfoxaflor.

253 Based on each dose-response curve, the 50% effect concentration (EC₅₀) and corresponding 95 %
254 confidence interval were determined. The effect concentrations and slope of each curve was compared
255 with a f-test using the command compParm from the drc-package (Ritz et al., 2015). The significance
256 level for both EC₅₀ values and slope was 0.05.

257 An Independent Action (IA) model was applied to the eight chosen endpoints to calculate the chemical,
258 predator, and/or increased temperature impact on the organisms' vitality. We expected the stressors to act
259 in a response additive way. Deviations in observed values from the modelled value were interpreted as
260 positive (when lower) and negative (when higher). For the treatment combining all three stressors,
261 responses of the individual stressors were used for the model. The model was as followed (Loewe et al.,
262 1926):

$$263 \quad E_{mix} = \prod^i \left(1 - \frac{e_i - e_{control}}{e_{max} - e_{control}} \right)$$

264 E_{mix} is the predicted effect of the joint stress, e_i is the observed effect of the single stressor i, e_{control} being
265 the effect observed under control conditions, and e_{max} is the maximum effect that is possible. For survival
266 data, e_{max} was set at 0. For other endpoints where a maximum effect of zero was not meaningful, this was
267 set as the largest observed effect.

268 As the actual measured concentrations of sulfoxaflor varied between scenarios, the individual stress of the
269 chemical on each endpoint was estimated based on the dose-response relationships under standard
270 conditions (20 °C and absence of predation cues). For the endpoints, mean emergence day and adult size,
271 the expected values were hence extrapolated from effects in 80 µg/L, as no adults were observed in the
272 highest nominal concentration of 160 µg/L.

273

274 3 Results:

275 3.1 Water chemistry and verification of test setup

276 Water chemistry parameters in the exposure solutions were not affected by the addition of sulfoxaflor, rise
277 in temperature, or the addition of predation cues. All measured pH values were within the range of 7.5 to
278 8.2, and salinities were measured to be below 2 ‰ for all treatments. Dissolved oxygen was above 90 %
279 saturation, independent of concentration or scenario treatment. Measurements of sulfoxaflor
280 concentrations found an average of 60 % recovery in the treatments. No differences in sulfoxaflor
281 recoveries were found over time or between scenarios. All measures related to water chemistry can be
282 found in the *supplementary information (supplementary information, B)*. For all scenarios, culture controls
283 of *C. riparius* were included to ensure stable conditions for the vitality of the tested organisms at all
284 timeslots. Survival on day 8 and total emergence after 23 days were not impacted over time, and all
285 culture controls showed over 70 % total emergence, validating the test setup according to the OECD
286 guideline (OECD, 2004). However, some minor differences were found when assessing the behavioural
287 endpoints (see *supplementary information, Figure C.1*), and therefore, all results were normalised to each
288 exposure scenario's respective culture control.

289

290 3.2 Effect values

291 Dose-response relationships and corresponding EC₅₀ values were estimated separately per scenario and
292 per endpoint (*Table 1*). We found few significant differences in EC₅₀ values per endpoint across different
293 scenarios (see *supplementary information, Table D.1*). The exception is total emergence, where the
294 standard exposure scenario (20 °C and absence of predation cues) showed significantly lower EC₅₀ values
295 compared to the other scenarios. However, it should be noted that there were relatively large confidence
296 intervals in most of the measured endpoints.

297 Sensitivities among endpoints differed slightly across scenarios. Overall, total emergence was the most
298 sensitive of the conventional endpoints, with EC₅₀ values ranging from 15 µg/L in the standard exposure

299 scenario to 79 µg/L sulfoxaflor in the scenario at 20 °C and presence of predation cues. Noteworthy, all
300 scenarios were found to have steep dose-response curves for this endpoint, with no emerging adults found
301 in any scenario for the highest concentration (all modelled dose-response curves can be found in
302 *supplementary information, Figure D.1*). The standard exposure scenario showed no or low dose-
303 dependent effect on mean emergence date and larval growth (*Table 1*).

304 For the standard exposure scenario, all behavioural endpoints (swimming, speed, and exploration) showed
305 EC₅₀ values between 20 to 50 µg/L, making them less sensitive than the most sensitive standard endpoint:
306 total emergence (*Table 1*). However, for the three additional stress scenarios, estimated EC₅₀ values were
307 either lower or in a similar range as the total emergence, except for exploration at 20 °C in presence of
308 predation cues and swimming time at 23 °C in presence of predation cues (*Table 1*). In addition, effects of
309 sulfoxaflor on adult size were within a similar sensitivity range as the behavioural endpoints for the three
310 stress scenarios.

311 *Table 1. Effect values of 50% effect (EC₅₀) on C. riparius exposed to sulfoxaflor under four different stress scenarios and for selected endpoints.*

Scenario	20 °C No Predation		23 °C No Predation		20 °C Predation		23 °C Predation		
	Endpoint	EC ₅₀ µg/L (CI)	P value	EC ₅₀ µg/L (CI)	P value	EC ₅₀ µg/L (CI)	P value	EC ₅₀ µg/L (CI)	P value
Conventional endpoints	Survival	3,8 (0 – 43,000)	0.84	110 (85 – 140)	< 0.001	13 (91 – 160)	< 0.001	120 (91 – 160)	< 0.001
	Total emergence	14 (0 – 45)	0.34	72 (66 – 77)	< 0.001	79 (72 – 86)	< 0.001	74 (65. – 83)	< 0.001
	Mean emergence day	15 (NaN)	NaN	35 (0 - 110)	0.34	150 (NaN)	NaN	31 (NaN)	NaN
	Growth	320 (0 – 3,600)	0.84	200 (0 – 86)	0.54	820 (7.0 – 160)	0.03	86 (75 – 97)	< 0.001
Non-conventional endpoints	Size of adult	0.24 (NaN)	NaN	160 (0 – 2,400)	0.88	82.(0 - 330)	0.49	76 (0 - 220)	0.29
	Swimming	36 (0 – 160)	0.57	100 (0 – 450)	0.56	104 (0 – 1,30)	0.86	180 (NaN)	NaN
	Speed	47 (0 – 100)	0.08	64 (56 – 72)	< 0.001	82.0 (0 – 990)	0.85	63(1.0 – 130)	0.047
	Exploration	22 (0 – 230,000)	0.99	734 (0 – 160)	0.08	5340 (0 – 10,000)	0.91	60 (40 – 79)	< 0.001

312 Legend: 20 °C No Predation = standard conditions of 20 °C without the addition of predation cues, 23 °C No Predation = exposed to 23 °C without
 313 the addition of predation cues, 20 °C Predation = exposed at 20 °C in presence of predation cues, 23 °C Predation = exposed to 23 °C in presence
 314 of predation cues. CI = confidence intervals, NaN= values could not be established. Non-conventional endpoints chosen were all related to
 315 biomechanistic endpoints.

316

317 3.3 Independent action

318 When comparing differences between observed and modelled responses using the IA model, we found
319 that conventional endpoints, overall, showed either limited differences with the standard exposure
320 scenario or a larger observed than expected value (*Figure 3; Table 2*). Here, low values for the measured
321 endpoints are regarded as a potential effect of the organisms. Generally, the higher the values, the better
322 we regard the animal's fitness. For example, high total emergence would mean that the organisms could
323 survive and thrive to adulthood, increasing the potential to reproduce and benefitting the population.
324 Besides mean emergence days, significant correlations between expected and observed values were found
325 for the conventional endpoints (*Table 2*). However, when the model predicted low values, observed values
326 still showed varying but limited effects, making the slope of the correlation relatively flat (see
327 *supplementary information, Figure E.1*). Some exemptions were found in larval length, mean emergence
328 day and total emergence, especially for higher concentrations of sulfoxaflor, where the observed values
329 were lower than expected (*Figure 3*). Furthermore, the conventional endpoints showed limited differences
330 between the exposure scenarios (*Table 2*).

331 In contrast to the conventional endpoints, all four non-conventional endpoints showed significant
332 deviations from the 1:1 observed expected values (*Table 2*). For biomechanistic endpoints, swimming
333 time, swimming velocity and exploration, negative correlations between observed and expected values
334 were found for all concentrations of sulfoxaflor and across all three stress scenarios (*Figure 3;*
335 *supplementary information, Figure E.1*). For adult size, strong correlations were observed across all three
336 exposure scenarios (*Table 2*), however, only minor deviations between observed and expected values were
337 found, with, in general, minor effects on adult size (see *supplementary information, Figure E.1*). The
338 difference between observed and IA-predicted effects seemed to depend on scenarios for several of the
339 endpoints including swimming time and velocity, where the combination of high temperature and
340 predation cues showed the highest negative deviations between observed and expected values (*Figure 3*),
341 and the lowest correlations; Spearman ρ is 0.44 ($p=0.015$) and 0.55 ($p=0.002$), respectively (*Table 2*). This

342 tendency did not seem to depend on sulfoxaflor concentration (*Figure 3*). Instead, high swimming values
343 were expected based on increased temperature and predation cues alone. In contrast, these effects were not
344 observed in combined treatments (see *supplementary information, Figure E.1*). Interestingly, for
345 exploration and adult size, the difference between observed and expected values became more evident in
346 higher sulfoxaflor concentrations, indicating that potential stress on stress responses depends on
347 compound concentrations (*Figure 3*).

348 In brief, negative deviations from additive responses were not observed for conventional endpoints but
349 were observed when focusing on biomechanistic endpoints. This illustrates the added value and
350 importance of explaining sensitivity, making use of non-conventional endpoints for neurotoxin exposure
351 at realistic environmental concentrations. This added value was most dominant when larvae were exposed
352 to the combination of all three stressors: sulfoxaflor, increased temperature, and predation stress. Lastly,
353 the higher the concentration of sulfoxaflor, the stronger the influence of environmental factors was.

354
 355 *Figure 3, Visual representation of additive effects based on the Independent Action model. The differences between observed and expected values*
 356 *explain deviations from additivity and, hence, represent other types of joint effects. Data was normalised and shown as differences to the standard*
 357 *exposure scenario (20 °C and absence of predation cues). Blue ▲ = 23°C and no predation cues, yellow ■ = 20°C and added predation cues,*
 358 *orange ● = 23°C and added predation cues. Error bars represent standard error (SE).*

359

360 *Table 2. Spearman rank correlations between observed and expected values for the three stress scenarios.*

Scenario	Endpoint	23 °C No Predation			20 °C Predation			23 °C Predation		
		df	ρ	P value	df	ρ	P value	df	ρ	P value
Conventional endpoints	Survival	28	0.523	0.003	28	0.453	0.012	28	0.387	0.035
	Total emergence	28	0.789	<0.001	28	0.819	<0.001	28	0.771	<0.001
	Mean emergence day	20	-0.275	0.216	23	0.391	0.053	23	0.065	0.756
	Growth	28	0.725	<0.001	28	0.806	<0.001	28	0.797	<0.001
Non-conventional endpoints	Size of adult	19	0.747	<0.001	23	0.694	<0.001	22	0.737	<0.001
	Swimming	28	0.770	<0.001	28	0.644	<0.001	28	0.439	0.015
	Speed	28	0.863	<0.001	28	0.614	<0.001	28	0.554	0.002
	Exploration	28	-0.819	<0.001	28	-0.696	<0.001	28	-0.785	<0.001

361 Legend: 23 °C No Predation = exposed to 23 °C and without the addition of predatory cue, 20 °C Predation = exposed at 20 °C and the addition of
 362 predation cues, 23 °C Predation = exposed to 23 °C and addition of predation cues. Statistic abbreviations: df = degrees of freedom, ρ =
 363 Spearman's rank correlation coefficient.

364

365

366 4 Discussion:

367 4.1 Effects of single stressors

368 In the present study, the toxicity of sulfoxaflor on *C. riparius* at standard test conditions was determined
369 by dose-response curves for eight different endpoints for which non-conventional endpoints were most
370 sensitive. Standardised endpoints of emergence (OECD, 2004) had an EC₅₀ value of 14.6 µg/L, in line
371 with previous studies reporting an EC₅₀ of 18.3 µg/L for total emergence (Rasmussen et al., 2024).
372 Robustness and replicability were further confirmed for another chironomid species, *Chironomus*
373 *kiinensis* larvae, with EC₅₀ on emergence at 20 µg/L (Liu et al., 2021).

374 When exposing the larvae to increased temperature without the influence of other stressors, we did not
375 observe any deviations from already expected effects on development. Increasing the temperature to 23 °C
376 compared to standard conditions at 20 °C significantly increased the growth of the larvae and resulted in
377 faster emergence. Length at day 10 was increased to 1.04 cm (±0.03) at 23 °C compared to 0.91 cm
378 (±0.03) at 20 °C and mean emergence day was at day 14 (±0.7) and 17 (±0.4) for 23 °C and 20 °C,
379 respectively (see *supplementary information, Figure C.2*). Based on previous literature, lower mean
380 emergence times in higher temperatures were expected as Heye et al. (2019) showed faster female
381 emergences already at 22 °C. They also found that faster emergence at higher temperatures could come
382 with a trade-off, resulting in smaller adults. However, we did not observe any significant changes in adult
383 size, nor larval survival and total emergence (see *supplementary information, Figure C.2*). Contrary to
384 known literature on one similar species, we did not find significant changes for any of the behavioural
385 endpoints when elevating the temperature. Increased temperature has been shown to cause hyperactivity in
386 Chironomidae larvae (*Diamesa zernyi*), with significant increases in both travelled distance and velocity
387 resulting from 72 h of exposure (Lencioni et al., 2021). Interspecies differences, or longer exposure
388 periods giving the larvae time to acclimate, could explain the discrepancies (Shaw, 2020). Based on our
389 observations, increasing the temperature to 23 °C did not seem to impact the *C. riparius* adversely.

390 Exposure to predation and alarm cues without other stressors did not cause any significant changes across
391 the eight endpoints investigated in this study (see *supplementary information, Figure C.2*). Exposure to
392 similar levels of predation stress has been found to lower the activity of *C. riparius* (Pestana et al., 2009;
393 Van Praet et al., 2014) as a survival mechanism to avoid falling prey to predators (Hölker & Stief, 2005).
394 The lack of response to the individual stressor might be due to low levels of predation cues or genetic
395 variances within *C. riparius* cultures (Nowak et al., 2007). In the present study, a long-standing culture of
396 chironomids was used; we assumed the responses to predation cues would be inherent (Tiselius et al.,
397 1995; Pestana et al., 2009). Lower activity, as a response to avoid predation, might impact the larvae's
398 feeding behaviour (Holker & Stief, 2005), leading to higher vulnerability. Hence, mechanistically, it is
399 interesting to investigate further if it is related to biomechanistic or energy-related explanations.

400

401 4.2 Joint effects

402 Based on the dose-response curves and comparison of corresponding effect values, significant differences
403 between scenarios were only found for the standard exposure scenario compared to all other scenarios for
404 total emergence and for swimming speed, when compared to increased temperature and the addition of
405 predation cues (see *supplementary information, Table D.1*). For the standard exposure scenario, the
406 highest effects were found to occur between 19 and 99 µg/L. Still, adding additional stressors in the form
407 of increased temperature and predation cues did not decrease the observed EC₅₀s. Rather, for total
408 emergence and swimming behaviour, where significant differences in EC₅₀ values were observed, the
409 standard exposure scenario had the highest sensitivities compared to the stress scenarios. Likewise,
410 Pestana et al. (2009) found high sensitivities to imidacloprid on *C. riparius*. However, no interactions
411 between the chemical and perceived predation risk were observed in any of the measured endpoints
412 (Pestana et al., 2009). While some studies have explored the combined effects of increased temperatures
413 or predation stress and chemical exposure (e.g., Xia et al., 2015; de Alkimin et al., 2020; Lencioni et al.,
414 2021), these investigations typically involved only one additional stressor in conjunction with chemical

415 exposure. Thus, the understanding of how multiple environmental stressors interact with neurotoxic
416 effects on aquatic species' behaviour, and thus population dynamics, remains incomplete, even though it is
417 known that there is a discrepancy between standard toxicity results and those results collected under more
418 environmental increased realism.

419 To further investigate the nature of these stressors' interactions, we used the IA model to predict effects
420 and compare them to actual observed responses on each endpoint (see *Figure 3*). For the conventional
421 endpoints as larval mortality, growth, and emergence, we found that most responses showed either lower
422 or additive effects when exposed to increased temperature and/or predation stress. Effects of simulated
423 predation stress in combination with a neurotoxic insecticide have been shown to cause similar tendencies,
424 with only detected effects on acetylcholinesterase (AChE) activity being additive (Van Praet et al., 2014).
425 In general, results from the conventional endpoints showed that using effect addition to predict the
426 environmental effects of multiple stressors seems a reliable and conservative method.

427 In contrast, for the non-conventional endpoints, the three biomechanistic endpoints showed negative
428 deviations between modelled and observed values for all combinations of stressors. Furthermore, the
429 effects on the size of the adults and exploration seem to depend on sulfoxaflor concentrations, with
430 exaggerated effects being potentiated in higher concentrations. Noteworthy, these enhanced effects were
431 not predicted by the conventional endpoints, meaning standard testing does not pick up potentially adverse
432 effects on natural populations.

433 The non-conventional endpoints tested here are important predictors of population dynamics. The size of
434 female adults in *Chironomus sp.* is directly correlated with their reproductive outcome, where bigger
435 females, in general, show both higher fecundity and hatching rates compared to their smaller counterparts
436 (Sibley et al., 2001; Marziali et al., 2019). Additionally, lower explorative behaviour of *C. riparius* is
437 likely to impact feeding abilities. As *C. riparius* are detritus feeders, leaving their protective burrow in the
438 sediment to eat is important for survival (Karima, 2001; Holker & Stief, 2005). Furthermore, low feeding
439 regimes have been shown to directly impact larval development and decrease the weight of female adults

440 (Silva et al., 2022). The same study also found that the effects of microplastics on *C. riparius* were
441 exaggerated under severe food shortages (Silva et al., 2022). Exploring how locomotive endpoints such as
442 exploration might impact the effects of chemicals through e.g. feeding could become important in future
443 studies to better understand and predict these environmentally relevant effects.

444 Enhanced effects of sulfoxaflor on swimming time and swimming velocity of *C. riparius* were found
445 across all stress scenarios and concentrations. Unpredicted decreases in swimming velocity can have
446 important consequences on species population dynamics, especially related to predator-prey interactions
447 (Weis et al., 2001; Moore et al., 2019). Impaired mobility of *C. riparius* has been directly linked to
448 increases in predation rates by zebrafish (*Danio rerio*), as the *C. riparius* were less likely to hide in
449 protective burrows, leaving them vulnerable to predation (Langer-Jaesrich et al., 2010). Hence,
450 disregarding these effects on swimming behaviour could lead to an underestimation of the effects of
451 sulfoxaflor on population dynamics in a multispecies environment such as a natural ecosystem where
452 predators are present.

453 Finally, some of the endpoints show that the combination of all three stressors has the most negative
454 differences between observed and estimated responses, indicating that a mixture of all three stressors is
455 the most likely to show potentially exaggerated effects. By definition, populations in field settings deal
456 with a multitude of joint stressors. Underestimating the effects on these endpoints could cause indirect
457 effects on natural populations, where standard laboratory approaches will not pick up the impacts as they
458 are executed with organisms exposed to single stressors.

459

460

461 5 Conclusions:

462 In conclusion, our results show that the conventional endpoint; emergence of *C. riparius* is sensitive to the
463 effects of sulfoxaflor, confirming their importance for standard toxicity testing. However, we also
464 demonstrated that conventional endpoints do not pick up on possible stronger effects of sulfoxaflor in
465 combination with environmental stressors. We observed increased effects of sulfoxaflor and a
466 combination of stressors (increased temperature and predation cues) on the size of emerged adults,
467 exploration behaviour of the larvae, and swimming behaviour that we could not explain solely by the
468 Independent Action model. Furthermore, this tendency seems to be more pronounced at higher
469 concentrations of sulfoxaflor for adult size and exploration, indicating possible concentration-dependent
470 effects. This highlights the importance of non-conventional biomechanistic endpoint screening to
471 determine ecologically relevant individual and population-level impacts under environmentally relevant
472 exposure conditions.

473

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481

482 **Declaration of competing interest**

483 The authors declare no competing interests.

484

485 **Ethical statements**

486 All experiments were executed at Lund University and in according to the ethics board of the Faculty of
487 Science, University Leiden. Fish cue was taken from fish at Lund University with the approval of fish
488 permit licence.

489

490 **Author statement**

491 **Sofie Rasmussen:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Software, Investigation, Data
492 curation, Writing – original draft, Writing - review & editing, Visualization. **Thijs Bosker:**
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496 Investigation, Data curation, Writing - review & editing. **Martina Vijver**: Conceptualization,
497 Methodology, Formal analysis, Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding
498 acquisition.

499

500 **Data**

501 Supplementary information is provided. The raw data files can be obtained upon request.

502

503 **Declaration of the use of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies**

504 During the preparation of this work the author(s) used ChatGPT to aid in the writing process and to get a
505 more cohesive language throughout the manuscript. Furthermore, ChatGPT were used for the preparation
506 of R scripts for statistical analyses. After using this tool/service, the author(s) reviewed and edited the
507 content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the content of the publication.

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Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Exposure conditions

Figure 2

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